

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

AGRONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS

Evaluation of rice germplasm for some panicle and grain characteristics

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Collection, maintenance, and characterization of important traits are extremely useful to any crop breeding program. Many rice varieties were collected from different parts of the Casamance region in southern Senegal, and agronomic traits were characterized at Djibélór Agricultural Research Center.

Variations in panicle type, secondary ramification of panicle branches, lemma and palea pubescence, and grain awning

Table 1. Variability of panicle and grain traits of some rices from southern Senegal, expressed as varietal frequency on a 1-9 scale according to IBPGR-IRRI Rice Advisory Committee handbook.

Character	Varietal frequency on the scale								
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Shattering			81		36				
Panicle fertility	128		74				12		
Endosperm type	110	100	4						

Table 2. Variability in 1,000-seed weight of rice from southern Senegal.

Character	Varietal frequency in the range								
	19	19.1- 21.0	21.1- 23.0	23.1- 25.0	25.1- 27.0	27.1-	29.1-	31.1-	33.1
1,000-seed wt	6	13	31	47	47	23			

were low. Variability in shattering, panicle fertility, endosperm type, and

1,000-seed weight is shown in Tables 1 and 2. *S*

Agronomic and yield characteristics of Topolea rices in western Romania

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We evaluated eight production-intensive Topolea rice lines in western Romania (Banloc rice fields). The lines have favorable, modern agronomic characteristics and were developed at IAS from local and introduced parents (Table 1). The lines were derived from hybrid combinations of three to four genotypes from different ecogeographic zones, including southwest Europe, southeast Europe, and northeast Asia.

All but Topolea 57-77, released in 1977, were released in 1976. Careful evaluation from 1979 to 1981 compared varietal performance with that of high-yielding local varieties Timis and Diamant. The new Topolea lines yielded higher (Table 2).

Topolea lines have semidwarf stature, with height ranging from 50 to 59 cm

Table 1. Topolea hybrid combinations, Banloc, Romania.

Line	Parentage	Year in control field
Topolea 57/17	Shin-Ei/Balila//Mimasari/Balila	1977
Topolea 58/76	Balico//Balila/Sesia 28 L.64///Krasnordar 424	1976
Topolea 60/76	Mimasari/Balila//Krasnordar 424	1976
Topolea 64/76	Shin-Ei/Balila//Krasnordar 424/Shin-Ei	1976
Topolea 66/76	Shin-Ei/Balila//Beco/Mantovo Vialone	1976
Topolea 70/76	Yuukara//Mimasari/Balila	1976
Topolea 71/76	Mimasari/Balila//G. Marchetti/Mantovo Vialone	1976
Topolea 88/76	Mimasari/Balila//Krasnordar 424/Shin-Ei	1976

Table 2. Yield and agronomic characteristics of Topolea lines, Banloc, Romania.

Line, variety	Plant ht (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Spikelets (no./panicle)	Panicle wt (g)	Duration (d)	Av yield 1979-80 (t/ha)
Topolea 57/77	56	13	122	1.8	113	8.4
Topolea 58/76	54	14	102	1.4	105	7.6
Topolea 60/76	59	14	120	2.1	119	8.6
Topolea 64/76	53	14	112	1.7	114	8.1
Topolea 66/76	53	13	150	2.3	121	8.0
Topolea 70/76	50	14	107	1.8	115	7.3
Topolea 71/76	58	15	157	2.0	123	7.7
Topolea 88/76	56	15	146	2.4	113	8.5
Av	55	14	127	1.9	115	8.0
Timis ^a 63	18		84	1.7	105	6.4
Diamanta	—	—	—	—	—	7.7

^aVarieties that are presently most productive. Diamant is the recently certified and approved variety.

(av 55 cm). Timis grows to 63 cm. The lines have short, dense, heavy panicles,

averaging 127 spikelets/panicle, each panicle weighing 1.9 g. Duration ranges